

Volumetric, acoustic, viscometric, and spectroscopic properties for binary mixtures of dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + *n*-alkylamine mixtures at 298.15 K

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Abstract : The excess molar volume (V_m^E), ultrasonic speed (u), and dynamic viscosity (η) have been measured in dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine, dibutylamine, and tributylamine across their entire composition ranges at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure. The density values derived from the excess molar volumes were converted to molar volumes (V) which are combined with the speed of sound to obtain estimates of the product $K_{S,m}$, and their excess counterparts $K_{S,m}^E$. In all mixtures the excess molar volumes are negative and symmetric across the entire composition range. The $K_{S,m}^E$ values are positive for all mixtures. The deviation of the speeds of sound u^D from their ideal values u^{id} in an ideal mixture were also calculated for all measured mole fractions. Viscosities have also been measured for mixtures of dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether and butylamine, dibutylamine, or tributylamine at the same temperature. From the experimental data, the deviation in the viscosity η from $\sum x_i \ln \eta_i$ and excess energies of activation for viscous flow (ΔG^{*E}) have been derived for all systems. The Flory theory of mixtures provides a useful basis for a quantitative interpretation of the viscosity results. The theoretical values of molar isentropic compressibility ($K_{S,m}$) and of speed of sound (u) have been estimated using the Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP) theory with the van der Waals (vdW) potential energy model and the results have been compared with experimental values.

Keywords : Binary mixtures, dynamic viscosity, spectroscopy, ultrasonometry.

As part of our program of research on thermodynamic, acoustic, and transport properties of binary mixtures containing alkoxypropanols, we have recently reported excess molar volumes, viscosities, and speeds of sound measurements of binary mixtures of alkoxypropanols either with *n*-alkylamines^{1,2}, 1-alkanols³⁻⁶ or amides⁷. In this work, we report new experimental data for the excess molar volumes (V_m^E), speeds of sound (u) and viscosities (η) of {dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) + butylamine (BA), dibutylamine (DBA), and tributylamine (TBA)} over the whole composition range at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure. The excess volume curves are symmetrical at $x_1 = 0.5$ for all mixtures. The experimental viscosity data are used to calculate deviation in viscosity ($\Delta \ln \eta$) and excess energies of activation (ΔG^{*E}) for viscous flow of the mixtures. An attempt is also made to study the internal structure of mixtures of alkoxypropanol with amine, correlating the volumetric properties and IR studies of the same binary mixtures (at equimolar composition).

An appropriate analysis of results can be achieved by applying Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP)⁸⁻¹¹ statistical

theory of non-electrolyte liquid mixtures. However, the PFP theory is applicable to non-associated liquids or liquid mixtures. The PFP theory is quite useful in predicting the excess function for binary mixtures of non-electrolyte liquids comprising alkanes, aromatic hydrocarbons, di-*n*-propyl ether, trialkylamines, etc. However the problem becomes more complex for liquid mixtures where one or both the components are associated in the pure state and where both the components interact. Since the mixtures investigated involve components of different chemical nature, shape and size, and also less possible interaction. Keeping this in view, the V_m^E values have been analyzed on the basis of PFP theory in order to examine in detail its predicting ability for the isentropic compressibilities and speeds of sound in a number of binary mixtures comprising dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether and mono-, di- and tributylamine.

The isentropic compressibilities κ_s for all mixtures were estimated by combining the densities derived from the excess molar volumes and the speeds of sound. The molar volume were multiplied by the isentropic compressibilities to obtain estimates of $K_{S,m}$. We have

also calculated the deviations u^D of the speeds of sound from those u^{id} in the ideal mixtures, together with the excess molar quantities $K_{S,m}^E$. The PFP theory with the van der Waals (vdW) energy model has been used for the theoretical estimation of the molar isentropic compressibility $K_{s,m}$ and speed of sound u of the binary liquid mixtures involving components of the different chemical nature, size and shape. The viscosities of the mixtures have been analyzed by means of the Bloomfield and Dewan¹² representation, based both on the free volume theory and the absolute reaction rate theory.

Experimental

Butylamine, dibutylamine, and tributylamine were obtained from S.D. fine chemical with a purity better than 99 mol%, respectively. All liquids were stored over sodium hydroxide pellets for several days and fractionally distilled twice^{13,14}. The middle fraction of the distillate was used. Dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (Aldrich, 99 mol%) was used without further purifications. Prior to experimental measurements, all liquids were stored in dark bottles over 0.4 nm molecular sieve to reduce water content, and were partially degassed with a vacuum pump under a nitrogen atmosphere. The estimated purities determined by gas chromatographic analysis were better than 99.5 mol% for all the liquid samples. The water content, measured for each sample by Karl-Fischer titration, was always found to be less than 0.002 mass%. Further, the purities of the liquids were checked by comparing the densities, viscosities, and speed of sound at 298.15 ± 0.01 K with their corresponding literature values¹⁵⁻²⁸ in Table 1.

Densities (ρ^*) of pure solvents were measured with a single stem pycnometer having a total volume of 8 cm^3 and an internal capillary diameter of about 0.1 cm. The reproducibility of the density measurements was better than $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The excess volumes were measured using a continuous dilution dilatometer similar to that described by Dickinson *et al.*²⁹. The details pertaining to calibration, experimental setup, and operational procedures are described elsewhere^{30,31}. The excess volumes were measured with an accuracy of $\pm 0.003 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ when tested with benzene and cyclohexane system as a reference at our working temperature. Each run just cover half of the mole fraction range so as to give an overlap between two runs. The mole fraction of each mixture was obtained with an uncertainty of 1×10^{-4} from the measured mass of one of the components. All masses were corrected for buoyancy. All molar quantities were based upon the IUPAC Table of atomic weights³².

The speeds of sound in both the pure liquids and their mixtures were measured at 4 MHz using NUSONIC (Mapco, Model 6080) velocimeter based on the sing-around technique³³ with a single transducer cell. The ultrasonic speeds at 298.15 K were directly obtained from the average round trip period of the ultrasonic waves in a fixed path length between the piezoelectric transducer and reflector. The maximal error in the measurements of the sound speed relative to water ($1496.687 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at 298.15 K)³⁴ is estimated to be less than 0.2 m s^{-1} . Further details concerning this apparatus, its calibrations, and operating procedure have been described previously^{35,36}.

Table 1. Observed and literature values of viscosities (η), densities (ρ^*), isobaric thermal expansivities (α_p^*), molar isobaric heat capacities ($C_{p,m}^*$), speeds of sound (u^*), and the product ($K_{S,m}$) of the molar volume and isentropic compressibility of pure liquid component 298.15 K

Components	ρ^* (kg m^{-3})		η (mPa.s)		α_p^* (kK^{-1})	$C_{p,m}^*$ ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	u^* (m s^{-1})		$K_{S,m}$ ($\text{mm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.			Obs.	Lit.	
	Dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether	900.02		0.993			0.996 ¹⁵	1.050 ^a	
Butylamine	733.30	733.23 ¹⁶ 733.25 ¹⁷ 733.35 ¹⁸	0.471	0.4700 ¹⁹ 0.496 ²⁰	1.257 ²¹	179.19 ²²	1248.2	1250 ¹⁶	87.30
Dibutylamine	757.53	757.72 ⁴ 755.95 ¹⁶	0.828		0.78 ²⁵	293.39 ²²	1244.5	1248 ¹⁶	145.42
Tributylamine	773.56	773.67 ²⁶ 773.78 ²⁸	1.265		0.990 ¹⁸	374.0 ¹⁹	1246.1	1246.9 ⁹	199.48

^aDerived from our measured densities.

^bCalculated using group additivity.

The kinematic viscosities of both the pure liquids and liquid mixtures were measured at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure using a Ubbelohde suspended-level viscometer³⁷. Experimental details have been given previously^{38,39}. The viscometer is filled with liquid or liquid mixtures, and its limbs are closed with Teflon caps, taking due precaution to minimize evaporation losses. The flow time measurements were made using an electronic stopwatch with a resolution of ± 0.01 s. An average of four or five sets of flow times was taken for each liquid and liquid mixtures. The caps of the limbs were removed during the measurements of flow times. The measured values of kinematic viscosities were converted to dynamic viscosities (η) after multiplication by the density. The reproducibility of dynamic viscosity results was found to be within ± 0.003 mPa.s. A thermostatically controlled, well-stirred water bath whose temperature was controlled to ± 0.01 K was used for all of the measurements. The IR spectra of the pure components and their equimolar mixtures were measured in neat using a scanning infrared spectrophotometer (M 500; Buck Scientific, Inc.,

USA), based on double beam performance having a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} provided with a sample space 150 mm^2 . The spectra was recorded at a temperature of 298.15 K using quartz crystal in the region 4000 cm^{-1} to 600 cm^{-1} .

Results and discussion

Results obtained experimentally for excess molar volumes of all binary mixtures over a range of mole fraction at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure are given in Table 2 and are graphically represented in Fig. 1. The speed of sound values are given in Table 3, together with the deviation u^D of the speed of sound from the values u^{id} calculated for ideal mixtures, the product of the molar volume and isentropic compressibility, and their corresponding excess molar quantity $K_{S,m}^E$.

The κ_s and $K_{S,m}$ were obtained from the relations :

$$\kappa_s = (\rho u^2)^{-1} = V(Mu^2)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{S,m}^E = -(\partial V/\partial p)_s = V\kappa_s = \sum x_i M_i / (\rho u)^2 \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density, V is the molar volume, x_i and M_i are the mole fraction and molar mass of component i in

Table 2. Excess molar volume (V_m^E) for (alkoxypropanol + n -alkylamine) systems at a temperature of 298.15 K

x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
CH₃[O(CH₂)₃]₂OCH₃ (1) + C₄H₉NH₂ (2)					
0.0226	0.007	0.3911	0.104	0.6577	0.085
0.0472	0.023	0.4304	0.105	0.7080	0.076
0.0764	0.037	0.4442	0.105	0.7081	0.076
0.1100	0.047	0.4812	0.104	0.7671	0.066
0.1611	0.059	0.4877	0.105	0.7701	0.066
0.2488	0.076	0.5195	0.105	0.8068	0.062
0.2640	0.086	0.5340	0.103	0.8507	0.059
0.2942	0.089	0.5646	0.100	0.8537	0.049
0.3047	0.094	0.5753	0.100	0.9007	0.040
0.3474	0.098	0.6016	0.093	0.9242	0.032
0.3482	0.099	0.6233	0.091	0.9480	0.016
0.3840	0.104	0.6561	0.087	0.9756	0.015
CH₃[O(CH₂)₃]₂OCH₃ (1) + (C₄H₉)₂NH (2)					
0.0335	0.057	0.4132	0.459	0.6674	0.438
0.0740	0.124	0.4649	0.475	0.7143	0.408
0.1117	0.177	0.4786	0.480	0.7466	0.384
0.1719	0.250	0.5210	0.482	0.8012	0.323
0.2192	0.299	0.5329	0.482	0.8325	0.289
0.2695	0.354	0.5697	0.480	0.8667	0.245
0.3070	0.392	0.5777	0.476	0.9034	0.180
0.3677	0.437	0.6084	0.471	0.9474	0.110
0.4103	0.460	0.6362	0.455	0.9766	0.049

CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃ (1) + (C ₄ H ₉) ₃ N (2)					
0.0045	0.020	0.4780	0.880	0.7049	0.760
0.0736	0.262	0.4852	0.884	0.7359	0.720
0.1224	0.398	0.5226	0.888	0.7730	0.650
0.1899	0.546	0.5679	0.877	0.8244	0.560
0.2625	0.671	0.5963	0.865	0.8644	0.466
0.3221	0.762	0.6261	0.845	0.8914	0.390
0.3823	0.825	0.6457	0.822	0.9277	0.280
0.4264	0.860	0.6723	0.796	0.9721	0.125

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes (V_m^E) for x_1 CH₃[O(CH₂)₃]₂OCH₃ + x_2 C₄H₉NH₂, (O); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₂NH, (□); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₃N, (Δ) at 298.15 K. The solid curves have been derived from eq. (10).

the mixture, respectively.

The excess quantities $K_{S,m}^E$ were calculated from :

$$K_{S,m}^E = K_{S,m} - K_{S,m}^{id} \quad (3)$$

where^{40,41} :

$$K_{S,m}^{id} = \sum x_i [K_{S,i}^* - T A_{p,i}^* \{ (\sum x_i A_{p,i}^* / \sum x_i C_{p,i}^*) - (A_{p,i}^* / C_{p,i}^*) \}] \quad (4)$$

where $A_{p,i}^*$, the product of the molar volume V_i^* and the isobaric expansivity $\alpha_{p,i}^*$, $C_{p,i}^*$, the isobaric molar heat capacity, and $K_{S,i}^*$, the properties of the pure liquid component i . The densities ρ of the mixture at the appropriate mole fraction used in the ultrasonic speed of sound measurements were obtained from molar volumes of pure

Table 3. Speed of sound (u), deviation from speed of sound (u^D) in an ideal mixture u^{id} ; the product ($K_{S,m}$) of the molar volume and isentropic compressibility, and the corresponding excess quantity ($K_{S,m}^E$) for alkoxypropanol + n -alkylamine systems at a temperature of 298.15 K

x_1	u (m s ⁻¹)	u^D (m s ⁻¹)	$K_{S,m}$ (mm ³ mol ⁻¹ MPa ⁻¹)	$K_{S,m}^E$ (mm ³ mol ⁻¹ MPa ⁻¹)
CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃ (1) + C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂ (2)				
0.0017	1247.5	-0.50	87.46	0.07
0.0036	1247.2	-0.57	87.57	0.08
0.0057	1246.9	-0.63	87.69	0.09
0.0159	1245.7	-0.66	88.22	0.11
0.0358	1243.5	-0.67	89.26	0.13
0.0659	1240.4	-0.70	90.82	0.15
0.0969	1237.5	-0.69	92.42	0.17
0.1245	1235.1	-0.70	93.85	0.19
0.1744	1231.1	-0.81	96.43	0.23
0.2615	1225.4	-0.80	100.90	0.27
0.3531	1220.6	-0.78	105.58	0.30
0.3751	1219.5	-0.87	106.71	0.32
0.4557	1216.3	-0.77	110.79	0.31
0.4908	1215.1	-0.71	112.55	0.30
0.5827	1212.3	-0.63	117.18	0.28
0.6261	1211.2	-0.55	119.35	0.25

Table-3 (contd.)

0.6705	1210.2	-0.45	121.56	0.22
0.7074	1209.4	-0.41	123.41	0.21
0.7393	1208.8	-0.33	124.99	0.18
0.8034	1207.6	-0.28	128.20	0.15
0.8504	1206.8	-0.27	130.55	0.14
0.9107	1205.9	-0.22	133.56	0.11
0.9186	1205.8	-0.20	133.95	0.10
0.9517	1205.4	-0.13	135.58	0.07
0.9640	1205.3	-0.07	136.18	0.04
0.9746	1205.2	-0.03	136.70	0.03
0.9863	1205.1	0.02	137.27	0.01
0.9923	1205.0	0.00	137.57	0.01
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$ (2)				
0.0025	1244.0	-0.33	145.49	0.09
0.0072	1243.6	-0.41	145.50	0.12
0.0112	1243.3	-0.44	145.50	0.14
0.0174	1242.8	-0.52	145.51	0.17
0.0314	1241.8	-0.58	145.49	0.23
0.0511	1240.3	-0.78	145.49	0.33
0.0726	1238.4	-1.28	145.56	0.50
0.1123	1235.2	-1.99	145.60	0.76
0.1609	1231.6	-2.67	145.60	1.02
0.2091	1228.5	-3.01	145.49	1.20
0.2591	1225.4	-3.39	145.36	1.37
0.3064	1222.9	-3.45	145.14	1.45
0.3345	1221.4	-3.56	145.02	1.51
0.4003	1218.3	-3.58	144.64	1.58
0.4421	1216.4	-3.65	144.38	1.62
0.4999	1213.9	-3.77	144.00	1.67
0.5532	1211.8	-3.83	143.60	1.67
0.6049	1210.1	-3.69	143.14	1.62
0.6572	1208.8	-3.27	142.57	1.47
0.7108	1207.6	-2.85	141.95	1.31
0.7563	1206.8	-2.30	141.38	1.14
0.8076	1206.0	-1.89	140.72	0.93
0.8472	1205.5	-1.47	140.18	0.76
0.8718	1205.3	-1.14	139.82	0.62
0.9155	1205.1	-0.46	139.14	0.36
0.9508	1205.0	0.08	138.58	0.14
0.9729	1204.9	0.38	138.23	0.01
0.9865	1204.9	0.57	138.00	-0.08
0.9929	1204.8	0.57	137.92	-0.11
0.9966	1204.8	0.62	137.85	-0.13
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$ (2)				
0.0026	1245.7	-0.31	199.44	0.12
0.0070	1245.2	-0.64	199.30	0.25
0.0116	1244.8	-0.86	199.12	0.36

Table-3 (contd.)

0.0152	1244.3	-1.22	199.04	0.49
0.0382	1242.6	-2.02	198.02	0.89
0.0702	1240.0	-3.37	196.65	1.48
0.0860	1238.6	-4.15	195.99	1.80
0.1106	1236.6	-5.18	194.90	2.23
0.1476	1233.6	-6.71	193.24	2.84
0.2099	1229.1	-8.73	190.20	3.63
0.2584	1225.5	-10.37	187.81	4.23
0.3071	1223.4	-10.50	187.93	4.34
0.3439	1220.0	-12.41	183.27	4.95
0.3835	1217.6	-13.19	181.09	5.20
0.4239	1215.5	-13.62	178.73	5.33
0.4484	1214.3	-13.81	177.27	5.37
0.5007	1212.4	-13.55	173.92	5.25
0.5519	1209.4	-14.41	170.94	5.42
0.6077	1207.7	-13.78	167.21	5.12
0.6546	1206.5	-13.01	163.98	4.78
0.7123	1205.0	-12.08	160.00	4.34
0.7578	1204.2	-10.95	156.74	3.88
0.7971	1203.3	-10.19	153.97	3.53
0.8534	1203.0	-8.10	149.73	2.76
0.9104	1203.1	-5.59	145.33	1.86
0.9350	1203.4	-4.25	143.36	1.41
0.9528	1203.6	-3.29	141.93	1.08
0.9705	1204.0	-2.15	140.46	0.70
0.9884	1204.4	-0.99	138.97	0.31
0.9954	1204.7	-0.40	138.36	0.12
0.9985	1204.8	-0.16	138.09	0.05

components and excess molar volumes from the cubic-spline interpolation.

The deviations of the speeds of sound from their values in an ideal mixture were calculated from^{41,42}.

$$u^D = u - u^{id} \quad (5)$$

where

$$u^{id} = V_m^{id} / (K_{S,m}^{id} \sum x_i M_i)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

The deviations of the viscosities were calculated from the relationship^{43,44} :

$$\Delta \ln \eta = \ln \eta - [x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2] \quad (7)$$

where η , η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the mixture and components 1 and 2, respectively.

The excess energies of activation for viscous flow were obtained with the following expression :

$$\Delta G^{*E} = RT [\ln (\eta V) - x_1 \ln (\eta_1 V_1) - x_2 \ln (\eta_2 V_2)] \quad (8)$$

where R and T are the gas constant and temperature, respectively. Data on derived densities, viscosities, and excess energies of activation for viscous flow for the various systems at 298.15 K are given in Table 4.

For compact and smooth representation of the results, the measured speeds of sound and viscosities were fitted to a polynomial of type :

$$Y(x) = \sum_{i=1} a_i x_i^{i-1} \quad (9)$$

by the method of least squares with each point weighted equally. The values of coefficients a_i and standard deviations σ are listed in Table 5(a).

For each mixture, the values of V^E , $K_{S,m}^E$, u^D , $\Delta \ln \eta$, and ΔG^{*E} were fitted to the Redlich-Kister type equation :

Table 4. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η), deviation in viscosities ($\Delta \ln \eta$), and excess energies of activation (ΔG^{*E}), for viscous flow of (alkoxypropanol + *n*-alkylamine) systems at a temperature of 298.15 K

x_1	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta \ln \eta$ (mPa.s)	ΔG^{*E} (J mol ⁻¹)	x_1	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	$\Delta \ln \eta$ (mPa.s)	ΔG^{*E} (J mol ⁻¹)
CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃ (1) + C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂ (2)									
0.0327	0.7428	0.486	0.008	36.11	0.4750	0.8361	0.706	0.051	240.32
0.0550	0.7490	0.497	0.013	59.72	0.5337	0.8451	0.737	0.050	231.41
0.0857	0.7572	0.511	0.018	84.66	0.5971	0.8541	0.770	0.047	214.13
0.1194	0.7658	0.527	0.024	114.04	0.6258	0.8581	0.786	0.046	210.39
0.1608	0.7758	0.548	0.031	144.86	0.6849	0.8657	0.817	0.040	187.88
0.2030	0.7854	0.569	0.038	174.66	0.7290	0.8712	0.842	0.037	169.82
0.2595	0.7974	0.596	0.042	193.25	0.7925	0.8786	0.878	0.032	142.82
0.3191	0.8091	0.626	0.046	218.82	0.8113	0.8807	0.889	0.030	134.49
0.3541	0.8156	0.643	0.048	223.23	0.8819	0.8883	0.929	0.022	93.19
0.3936	0.8227	0.663	0.049	223.93	0.9411	0.8943	0.964	0.014	55.11
0.4050	0.8246	0.669	0.049	229.56	0.9672	0.8969	0.976	0.007	28.61
CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃ (1) + (C ₄ H ₉) ₂ NH (2)									
0.0134	0.7594	0.828	-0.002	-5.11	0.4814	0.8258	0.878	-0.031	-74.74
0.0523	0.7650	0.829	-0.009	-19.61	0.5368	0.8337	0.885	-0.032	-74.95
0.0976	0.7714	0.835	-0.009	-20.54	0.6149	0.8448	0.898	-0.028	-72.62
0.1339	0.7766	0.837	-0.014	-30.74	0.6467	0.8493	0.905	-0.027	-66.35
0.1655	0.7811	0.840	-0.016	-36.27	0.7133	0.8588	0.923	-0.021	-43.12
0.2328	0.7907	0.848	-0.019	-41.50	0.7481	0.8637	0.931	-0.019	-38.74
0.2934	0.7992	0.855	-0.022	-47.41	0.8491	0.8782	0.954	-0.012	-26.29
0.3548	0.8079	0.862	-0.025	-53.85	0.9102	0.8870	0.972	-0.005	-8.40
0.4539	0.8219	0.875	-0.029	-56.42	0.9523	0.8931	0.981	-0.003	-4.24
0.4675	0.8239	0.876	-0.030	-57.96	0.9877	0.8982	0.990	-0.001	-2.17
CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃ (1) + (C ₄ H ₉) ₃ N (2)									
0.0216	0.7753	1.253	-0.004	-7.31	0.5639	0.8324	1.032	-0.067	-127.56
0.0434	0.7772	1.239	-0.010	-19.58	0.5863	0.8353	1.025	-0.068	-135.05
0.0720	0.7797	1.223	-0.017	-32.37	0.5908	0.8359	1.022	-0.068	-143.81
0.1218	0.7842	1.194	-0.028	-56.16	0.6441	0.8430	1.018	-0.061	-118.55
0.1719	0.7889	1.167	-0.039	-78.41	0.7027	0.8512	1.006	-0.059	-115.66
0.2211	0.7937	1.147	-0.044	-86.26	0.7530	0.8586	0.998	-0.053	-110.59
0.2719	0.7988	1.125	-0.052	-101.56	0.8027	0.8662	0.995	-0.046	-77.78
0.3159	0.8034	1.109	-0.056	-104.13	0.8592	0.8752	0.992	-0.035	-69.27
0.3804	0.8104	1.081	-0.065	-128.24	0.9048	0.8828	0.990	-0.027	-51.78
0.4235	0.8153	1.069	-0.066	-126.37	0.9378	0.8886	0.989	-0.019	-38.26
0.4607	0.8197	1.056	-0.068	-140.37	0.9704	0.8945	0.993	-0.007	-13.18
0.5066	0.8252	1.045	-0.068	-133.25					

$$F(x) = (x_1 x_2) \sum_{i=1}^k a_i (x_1 - x_2)^{i-1} \quad (10)$$

Values of coefficients a_i and the standard deviation σ are listed in Table 5(b). For mixtures, $\sigma (V_m^E) \leq 0.003$ for the precision attainable with the dilatometer used. Experi-

mental results for u , $K_{S,m}$, and u^D together with smoothed curves of them are shown in Figs. 2 to 4. There are no literature values of V_m^E , u or η for these mixtures available for comparison.

From Fig. 1, it can be seen that V_m^E is positive over the entire range of composition. In all mixtures, the mini-

Fig. 2. Composition dependence of experimental —, and PFP theory -----, values of speed of sound (u) for $x_1\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3 + x_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$, (I); + $x_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$, (II); + $x_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$, (III) at 298.15 K.

imum occurs around $x_1 = 0.5$. This contrasts with the behavior of negative V_m^E values for butylamine, or dibutylamine and dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether, dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether or dipropylene gly-

Table 5(a). Coefficients a_i of eq. (9) and standard deviations σ of (alkoxypropanol + n -alkylamine) systems at a temperature of 298.15 K

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	σ
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ (2)						
η (mPa.s)	0.471	0.467	0.057	0.003		0.001
u (m s^{-1})	1247.38	-109.25	107.95	-41.43		0.21
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$ (2)						
η (mPa.s)	0.827	0.072	0.051	0.047		0.002
u (m s^{-1})	1244.27	-85.09	50.99	-5.30		0.14
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$ (2)						
η (mPa.s)	1.265	-0.618	0.376	-0.031		0.002
u (m s^{-1})	1245.77	-85.54	27.00	17.33		0.28

col *tert*-butyl ether + n -alkanol^{3-5,48}, but consistent with that of the positive V_m^E results for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether or dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + tributylamine^{1,2}. Also, their behavior may be compared with the V_m^E results for mixtures of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether with alkylamine : V_m^E becomes more positive with the replacement of a hydrogen by a

Table 5(b). Coefficients a_i of eq. (10) and standard deviations σ of (alkoxypropanol + n -alkylamine) systems at a temperature of 298.15 K

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	σ
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$ (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	0.418	-0.091	-0.123	0.116	0.278	0.003
$\Delta \ln \eta$ (mPa.s)	0.201	-0.037	0.002	0.038	0.062	0.001
ΔG^{*E} (J mol^{-1})	930.3	-173.1	19.13	77.8	159.4	4
u^D (m s^{-1})	-2.54	1.58	-4.20	4.36		0.24
$K_{S,m}^E$ ($\text{mm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{MPa}^{-1}$)	1.24	-0.34	-1.03	-0.43	2.68	0.03
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$ (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	1.931	0.205	-0.182	0.035	0.311	0.003
$\Delta \ln \eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.120	-0.015	0.043	0.075		0.001
ΔG^{*E} (J mol^{-1})	-274.5	-88.4	262.0	304.2	-254.2	6
u^D (m s^{-1})	-14.78	-0.08	-8.92	14.24	18.97	0.25
$K_{S,m}^E$ ($\text{mm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{MPa}^{-1}$)	6.60	0.15	1.63	-3.26	-3.79	0.06
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3$ (1) + $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$ (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	3.545	0.214	-0.052	-0.011	1.012	0.003
$\Delta \ln \eta$ (mPa.s)	-0.272	-0.022	-0.009			0.001
ΔG^{*E} (J mol^{-1})	-539.23	-42.76	9.05			6
u^D (m s^{-1})	-56.31	-6.51	4.68	-4.04	-18.04	0.27
$K_{S,m}^E$ ($\text{mm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{MPa}^{-1}$)	21.62	-0.51	-2.28	0.53	6.59	0.08

Table 6. Characteristic parameters of pure components at a temperature of 298.15 K

Components	κ_T (TPa ⁻¹)	\bar{v}	\bar{T}	$V^* \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	T^* (K)	P^* (J m ⁻³)	$\chi_{12} \times 10$ (J m ⁻³)
CH ₃ [O(CH ₂) ₃] ₂ OCH ₃	801	1.2239	0.0532	171.10	5604	494	
C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂	556	1.2981	0.0642	76.85	4644	556	7.20
(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ NH	959	1.2008	0.0493	142.08	6048	350	21.46
(C ₄ H ₉) ₃ N	1021	1.2457	0.0567	192.35	5258	449	27.46

methyl group in the dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether chain. Again, the V_m^E is more positive for the system (dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + tributylamine). The positive values of V_m^E can be explained by considering the disruption of liquid order on mixing, and unfavorable interactions between unlike molecules.

The Prigogine-Flory-Patterson theory was used to correlate the V_m^E results for the present mixtures. The various parameters involved in the PFP theory for the pure components are listed in Table 6. The contact interaction parameter χ_{12} for each liquid mixture is obtained according to the PFP theory, from the excess molar volume values at $x_1 = 0.5$. These are listed in the last column of Table 6. The much larger positive values of the χ_{12} parameter for the dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + tributylamine system indicates the less possible chemical interaction as suggested from the V_m^E results.

Fig. 3 shows the plots of experimental $K_{S,m}^E$. The values of $K_{S,m}^E$ for all three dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + *n*-alkylamine mixtures are positive and decrease from tributylamine to butylamine. The trend of decrease

Fig. 3. Excess molar isentropic compressibilities ($K_{S,m}^E$) for x_1 CH₃[O(CH₂)₃]₂OCH₃ + x_2 C₄H₉NH₂, (O); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₂NH, (□); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₃N, (Δ) at 298.15 K. The solid curves have been derived from eq. (10).

ing $K_{S,m}^E$ from tributylamine to butylamine is similar to that observed in case of the V_m^E . This behavior may be compared with the $K_{S,m}^E$ results for mixtures dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether with amines : a large positive value and a marked increase in the magnitude of $K_{S,m}^E$ are evident here. The overall behavior $K_{S,m}^E$ is similar for u^D but with opposite sign. Also, the behavior of excess molar volume seems to be consistent with a maximum values of $K_{S,m}^E$ and a minimum value for u^D with dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether with tributylamine. This is normal because u is generally lower (at higher x_1) for low rigid structure. Although $K_{S,m}^E$ is positive, that is, the mixture is more compressible than the corresponding ideal mixture, suggesting that there may be less intermolecular interaction between the *n*-alkylamine and the ether. However, V_m^E is highly positive for tributylamine, although $K_{S,m}^E$ is positive and u^D is likewise negative (Fig. 4) from butylamine to tributylamine, indicating that when the mixtures are created "excess free volume" decreases and is lower in mixture containing dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether and tributylamine. This shows that interstitial accommodation does not play any important role by influencing the $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D of liquid mixtures containing alkylamines. So the molecular size and shape of

Fig. 4. Deviation in speed of sound (u^D) for x_1 CH₃[O(CH₂)₃]₂OCH₃ + x_2 C₄H₉NH₂, (O); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₂NH, (□); + x_2 (C₄H₉)₃N, (Δ) at 298.15 K. The solid curves have been derived from eq. (10).

the components are equally important factor here. The present results for $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D are also manifested through the results obtained with the excess molar volumes V_m^E .

Table 7. Shift in the position of C-O and N-H stretch in binary mixtures at $x_1 = 0.5$ ($\Delta v = v_{\text{mixt.}} - v_{\text{pure liquid}}$)

System	$\Delta v / (\text{cm}^{-1})$		
	C-O	N-H	
	(stretching)	(stretching)	(bending)
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3 + \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$	-0.6	+10.6	+2.3
		+32.0	
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3 + (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$	+1.4	+36.2	-1.0
$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_3]_2\text{OCH}_3 + (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$	+2.4		

In order to further understand molecular interactions of these systems, IR data at equimolar concentration for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine, + dibutylamine, and + tributylamine have been reported in Table 7. The shift in C-O stretch in dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) + butylamine (BA)} ($\Delta v = -6.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) increases to $\Delta v = 1.4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in {dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) + dibutylamine (DBA)}. This is again increased to $\Delta v = 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in {dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) + tributylamine (TBA)}, indicating more interaction in case of dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine as compared to other two mixtures. The Δv for C-O stretching is negative for mixture dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) with butylamine (BA), resulting negative shift in energy, ΔE . This indicates the existence of red shift in the spectra.

Pure butylamine (BA) gives two bands at 3368.1 cm^{-1} and 3296.1 cm^{-1} . Higher frequency band is due to asymmetric vibration. When dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME) is mixed with butylamine (BA), the two free N-H stretching vibration are shifted to slightly higher frequency given in Table 7. A low intensity shoulder appears at about 3000 cm^{-1} on the lower frequency side of the symmetric N-H stretching band in butylamine (BA).

This low intensity band has been attributed to an overtone of the N-H bending vibration that appears at 1607.1 cm^{-1} . Pure dibutylamine (DBA) gives one band in N-H stretching region at 3285.7 cm^{-1} . When dibutylamine (DBA) is mixed with dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME), the free N-H stretching vibration are shifted to slightly higher frequency given in the range $3500\text{--}3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Thus, from IR measurement we have confirmed that there is existence of interaction due to cross bonding of N-H---O between unlike molecules. This cross bonding decreases in the order : butylamine (BA) > dibutylamine (DBA) > tributylamine (TBA) with dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether (DPGDME). This supports with trends of the behavior of the V_m^E values. But in case of alkylamine + dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (DPGMME) and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (DPGMBE), it shows the energetic superiority of N---H-O structure compared to N-H---O.

The theoretical values of molar isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}^E$ and speed of sound u for both the liquid components and the liquid mixtures have been estimated using the van der Waals (vdW) potential energy model in the Prigogine-Flory-Patterson (PFP) theory. The relevant equations are given elsewhere^{8,10,49-52}. The experimental and the PFP estimates of both u and $K_{S,m}$ with the vdW energy model for all the binary mixtures at equimolar composition are summarized in Table 8(a). In order to perform a numerical composition of the estimation capability of the vdW energy model in the PFP theory, we calculated the standard deviation using the relation

$$\sigma = [\Sigma\{(\text{expt.} - \text{theor.})/\text{expt.}\}^2/(n - 1)]^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where n represents the number of experimental data. The values of σ are also given in Table 8(a). Values of $K_{S,m}^E$ and Δu^D at equimolar composition, denoted as $\Delta K_{S,m}^E$ and Δu^D , respectively are also listed in Table 8(b). The composition dependence of the experimental u , $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D have been compared graphically in Figs. 2 to 4 with

Table 8(a). Comparison of experimental and calculated values of the speed of sound u , and isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}$, of binary mixtures at $x_1 = 0.5$ and standard deviation at a temperature of 298.15 K

	u (m s^{-1})			$K_{S,m}$ ($\text{mm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$)		
	Experimental	vdW	σ	Experimental	vdW	σ
	$\text{CH}_3[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2]_2\text{OCH}_3 +$					
$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$	1214.5	1209.7	0.003	113.01	113.97	0.01
$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$	1213.8	1188.8	0.01	144.01	150.14	0.03
$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$	1212.0	1201.4	0.01	174.10	177.17	0.01

theoretically calculated PFP theory using vdW energy model.

Fig. 2 and Table 8(a) show that the theoretical values of speed of sound u and molar isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}$ for the vdW energy model agree very well with the experimental values within 0.01 and 0.03, respectively, dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine (I), and + dibutylamine (II), while for the mixture dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + tributylamine (III), the agreement is within 0.01 and 0.01, respectively, for u and $K_{S,m}$. Thus, agreement between the theoretical and the experimental u and $K_{S,m}$ for the mixture containing dibutylamine are not completely satisfactory.

Comparison of $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D results in Table 8(b) and Figs. 3 and 4 show $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D values estimated using the vdW energy model are quite good for the mixtures dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine. In the case of mixtures dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + dibutylamine and tributylamine, both $K_{S,m}^E$ and u^D deviate considerably, $K_{S,m}^E$ upto $6.14 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ and u^D upto -25.09 m s^{-1} .

Table 8(b). Comparison of the experimental excess molar isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}^E$ and deviation of speed of sound u^D with values calculated using the PFP theory {van der Waals (vdW)} for different equimolar mixtures at a temperature of 298.15 K

	$K_{S,m}^E$		u^D	
	$(\text{mm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ MPa}^{-1})$		(m s^{-1})	
	Experimental	vdW	Experimental	vdW
$\text{CH}_3\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OCH}_3 +$				
$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$	0.31	1.26	-0.63	-5.84
$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$	1.65	7.79	-3.70	-28.79
$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$	5.4	8.47	-14.08	-24.62

We have determined η and calculated $\Delta \ln \eta$ at 298.15 K. Table 4 reveals that η increases for all the mixtures with increasing mole fraction x_1 of ether. Fig. 5 shows that the deviation in viscosity $\Delta \ln \eta$ is positive for butylamine and negative for dibutylamine and tributylamine over the entire range of composition. In fact, a positive deviation over the entire range of composition for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine and a large negative deviation for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + tributylamine are observed. This behavior also finds support from the positive values of excess molar volumes and Flory contact interaction parameter χ_{12} (Table 6). Negative values of $\Delta \ln \eta$ for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + tributylamine or dibutylamine imply that (i) the mixtures are less viscous than the corresponding

ideal mixture and (ii) the unfavorable interactions⁵³ results in the positive V_m^E and negative ΔG^* shown in Fig. 1 and Table 4. The small positive ΔG^* for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + butylamine indicates the presence of weak interaction^{54,55} between molecules. This reveals that the strength of the interaction is not only the factor influencing the viscosity deviation of liquid mixtures. The molecular size and shape of the components also play an equally important role.

There are different expressions available in the literature to calculate η . Here we have applied the method of Bloomfield and Dewan¹².

Bloomfield and Dewan¹² developed the expression from the combination of the theories of free volumes and absolute reaction rate

$$\Delta \ln \eta = f(\bar{v}) - \Delta G^R/RT \quad (12)$$

where $f(\bar{v})$ is the characteristic function of the free volume defined by

$$f(\bar{v}) = 1/(\bar{v}-1) - x_1/(\bar{v}_1-1) - x_2/(\bar{v}_2-1) \quad (13)$$

and ΔG^R is the residual energy of mixing, calculated with the following expression⁴⁹

$$\Delta G^R = \Delta G^E + RT \{x_1 \ln (x_1/\phi_1) + x_2 \ln (x_2/\phi_2)\} \quad (14)$$

where ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are segment fraction defined by

$$\phi_2 = 1 - \phi_1 = x_2/[x_2 + x_1 (r_1/r_2)] \quad (15)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are in the ratio of respective molar core volumes V_1^* and V_2^* .

Fig. 5. Experimental viscosity deviations ($\Delta \ln \eta$) for $x_1 \text{ CH}_3\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OCH}_3 + x_2 \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NH}_2$, (O); $+ x_2 (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NH}$, (□); $+ x_2 (\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{N}$, (Δ) at 298.15 K. Continuous curves were calculated from eq. (10) for experimental data and from Bloomfield and Dewan data (12).

The excess energy can be obtained from the statistical theory of liquid mixtures proposed by Flory and co-workers and is given by :

$$G^{*E} = x_1 P_1^* V_1^* [1/(\bar{v}_1) - 1/(\bar{v}) + 3T_1 \ln \{(\bar{v}_1^{1/3} - 1)/(\bar{v}^{1/3} - 1)\}] + x_2 P_2^* V_2^* [1/(\bar{v}_2) - 1/(\bar{v}) + 3T_2 \ln \{(\bar{v}^{1/3} - 1)/(\bar{v}^{1/3} - 1)\}] + (x_1 \theta_2 V_1^* \chi_{12})/\bar{v} \quad (16)$$

where the various symbols used have their usual meanings.

Using the χ_{12} values from the fitting values of V_m^E and Table 6, we have calculated ΔG^R , and $f(\bar{v})$ and finally $\Delta \ln \eta$, according to the Bloomfield and Dewan relationship, which is compared with the experimental data (Fig. 5). Fig. 5 shows that the largest deviation between the estimated and experimental curves occurs for dipropylene glycol dimethyl ether + dibutylamine.

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